

MEDBUDDY

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ABSTRACT

The healthcare consultation services here in the Philippines continues to rely on manual, paper-based appointment scheduling and non-centralized medical record management which are the primary sources of inefficiencies, prolonged patient waiting times, inconvenience, and limited continuity of proper care. This study presents Medbuddy, a web-based clinical consultation and health records management system designed to address the shortcomings of traditional system through convenient, user-friendly, and centralized solution for appointment scheduling and digital health records system. Medbuddy is implemented using modern web technologies to support three primary stakeholders, namely, patients, clinical doctors, and clinical staff in a role-based access control framework. The role-based design ensures that data is securely handled, workflow is properly separated, and consultation is made seamless and well-coordinated. The system integrates four core functional modules: (1) centralized health records management system for storing medical histories, diagnoses, results and prescription; (2) consultation appointment scheduling that allows patients to request appointments based on availability of clinical doctors; (3) appointment status tracker and notification system that delivers automated confirmation, reminders and updates about appointment schedule; and (4) integrated messaging functionality that enables, efficiency, usability, and security.

KEYWORDS

Electronic Health Records, Online Consultation Appointment, Healthcare Services, Digital Management System, Web-based Clinics

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I. INTRODUCTION

Healthcare service delivery, particularly consultation services in clinics across many developing regions such as the Philippines, remains constrained by manual appointment scheduling, fragmented patient records, and limited post-consultation communication [1]. Traditional paper-based workflows often result in prolonged waiting times, administrative inefficiencies, data inconsistencies, and reduced continuity of care [2]. Studies have shown that fragmented medical documentation and poor coordination among healthcare stakeholders significantly contribute to misdiagnosis [3], delayed treatment, and decreased patient satisfaction [4].

With the advancement of information and communication technologies, especially the digitalization of management systems, electronic health systems have emerged as viable solutions to modernize healthcare workflows. Digital appointment scheduling, centralized electronic medical records (EMRs), and integrated communication platforms have demonstrated improvements in operational efficiency and patient service delivery [5]. However, many existing systems are either costly, complex, or poorly aligned with the specific needs and constraints of healthcare services in the country [6].

To address these potential gaps, this study presents MedBuddy, a web-based clinic consultation management system designed to digitalize appointment scheduling and health records management for clinics. MedBuddy provides a centralized, role-based platform for patients, clinical doctors, and clinic staff, enabling efficient consultation workflows, secure health information management, and real-time communication. The system aims to enhance accessibility, reduce administrative burden, and improve overall healthcare service delivery through an integrated and user-friendly digital solution as a part of promoting the Sustainable Development Goal Number 3: Good Health and Well-being.

The system is comprised of four main modules, each addressing the gaps identified: improve healthcare access for patient requiring consultation services {Ref07}, systematic appointment schedule management system for clinical services, centralized health records access for medical professionals, and messaging application for post-consultation communication. These functionality modules were identified by the researchers based on the comparative study that they conducted on various related digital applications. The system is also designed for the consultation process in the country, covering diverse range of patients in rural and urban areas, across various age groups and digital literacy. It is also adaptable to different types and sizes of healthcare service facilities, with its core functionalities including the important steps of conducting consultation related services.

METHODOLOGY

The development of Medbuddy followed a systematic flow adapted from the software development lifecycle (SDLC) incorporating the fundamental stages of planning, designing, implementing, testing, and evaluating phases in an iterative manner using Agile methodology shown in Figure 1. System development scheduling was managed by the researchers using Gantt charts and Program Evaluation Review Technique (PERT) diagrams to help define dependencies on tasks and projected timelines.

Figure 1. Agile SDLC Methodology.

I. Technical Requirements

Medbuddy was implemented as a web-based user interface which highlights flexibility on various devices used in clinical setup. The system development is composed of frontend development of various user interfaces using HTML, CSS, and Javascript programming languages. Backend development was implemented using PHP for request routing, role-based authentication with MySQL serving as the database

management deployed via XAMPP. This supported structured storage of user profiles, appointment records, medical records and consultation reports, and other related documents. Google Chrome was the main browsing engine used by the researchers for software testing.

For the hardware requirements, researchers used a programming laptop with at least 10 GB worth of free storage and 8 gigabytes of RAM. This is where integration of multiple libraries and trial runs of database management under local network.

II. System Architecture and Functional Design

Figure 2. Medbuddy Role Access Diagram.

Medbuddy employed a role-based access control system that provides different levels of access based on the four primary modules: health records management, consultation appointment scheduling, appointment status tracking and notification, and integrated messaging. The architecture focused on supporting three user roles in the system which are the patients, clinical doctors, and clinic staff. Figure 2 shows the access privilege distribution diagram of Medbuddy.

The system has four functionality modules described below:

- Health Records Management – acts as a repository for the electronic health records comprising of consultation histories, vital signs, laboratory results, diagnoses, and prescription records. The accessibility to the records follows the role access distribution in Figure
- Consultation Appointment Scheduling – this module allows patients to view real-time doctor availability and submit consultation schedule requests through a calendar-based interface. Clinic staff can moderate requests to ensure that there is no schedule conflicting while clinical doctors can configure their availability schedule.

c) Appointment Status Tracking and Notification – this module allows automation of confirmation messages and reminders referring to consultation schedule updates to reduce no-show appointments for reliable consultation experience.

d) Integrated Messaging – this module enables secure and traceable communication between clinics and patients especially on post-consultation stages where follow-up care, clarification of medical instructions, and inquiries is needed by both parties.

The modular design of the architecture highlights scalability, maintainability and clear separation of roles for the stakeholders in the system.

III. Testing and Evaluation Procedure

The system testing was conducted in accordance with the software testing standards from the International Organization for Standardization or ISO, specifically the ISO/IEC 9126 software quality standards [Ref08]. This specific standard provided the necessary attributes for proper testing of the system such as functionality, efficiency, usability, security, and maintainability. Multiple testing phases were conducted by the researchers which included unit testing, integration testing, and full system testing focusing on the overall technical performance of Medbuddy. Acceptance testing was also conducted by the researchers to measure and evaluate the user perception on technology acceptance.

Software testing verified the correctness of the functionalities in the system, evaluating whether each module has achieved the intended outcome. This includes evaluating the accurate appointment scheduling, reliable record storage, and consistent notification delivery. The general approach of the researchers for overall system functionality testing revolves on measuring number of correct outcomes over the total number of trials. Acceptance testing involved gathering data from respondents such as IT professionals, medical professionals, and patients using five-point Likert Scale.

RESULTS, DISCUSSIONS, AND IMPLICATIONS

This section presents the evaluation results from the software testing and acceptance testing of Medbuddy based on ISO/IEC 9126 software quality standards.

The software testing was based on ISO/IEC 9126 software quality model. Table 1 below shows the software performance testing of the modules of Medbuddy.

Product Features	Software Quality Models Attributes	Software Quality Internal Metrics	Percent Mean Score (%)	Overall Feature Percent Score (%)
Online Appointment Scheduling	Functionality (ISO/IEC-9126)	Accuracy	87.50%	88.91%
		Interoperability	88.64%	
		Security	95.45%	
		Suitability	84.09%	
Health Records management	Efficiency (ISO/IEC-9126)	Time behavior	87.50%	86.37%
		Resource utilization	85.23%	
Appointment Status Tracker and Notification	Usability (ISO/IEC-9126)	Understandability	87.27%	87.27%
		Learnability	86.36%	
		Operability	86.36%	
Integrated Messaging Function	Usability (ISO/IEC-9126)	Learnability	86.36%	86.36%
		Operability	86.36%	
		Attractiveness	83.18%	

Table 1. Software Testing Results.

The table shows that the four functionality modules were evaluated using the internal metrics of the attributes such as accuracy, efficiency, and usability. Results show that the online appointment scheduling, health records management, appointment status tracker, and integrated messaging function got a feature percent score of 88.91%, 86.37%, 87.27%, and 86.36% respectively. The scores were then interpreted using the metric interpretation table shown in Table 2 below.

Percent Mean Score Range (%)	Interpretation	Description
79.21 – 100.00	Very Good	The software quality metric rating reaches best expected levels.
59.41 - 79.20	Good	The software quality metric rating is at a satisfactory level and needs little improvement.
39.61 – 59.40	Average	The software quality metric rating is on a fair level; some improvements are needed.
19.81 - 39.60	Poor	The software quality metric rating is considered undesired; significant improvements are required.
1.00 - 19.80	Very Poor	Not acceptable; a major re-design is required.

Table 2. Mean Score Interpretation Table.

Based on the metric interpretation, the four functionality modules of Medbuddy obtained a Very Good rating which is interpreted as the software reaches best expected level. Security obtained the highest individual rating score at 95.45% indicating strong access control and data handling mechanisms.

II. ACCEPTANCE TESTING RESULTS

Similarly, the acceptance testing results shown in Table 3 show that Medbuddy was evaluated according to the acceptance attribute based on ISO/IEC 9126 including functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability.

The acceptance testing results based on ISO/IEC 9126 is shown in Table 3 below.

Acceptance Attribute	Criteria	Mean Score	Interpretation
System Functionality	Suitability	4.45	Very Good
	Accuracy	4.45	Very Good
	Interoperability	4.42	Very Good
	Security	4.53	Very Good
	Compliance	4.39	Very Good
Reliability	Maturity	4.38	Very Good
	Fault Tolerance	4.36	Very Good
	Recoverability	4.35	Very Good
Usability	Understandability	4.36	Very Good
	Learnability	4.40	Very Good
	Operability	4.45	Very Good
	Attractiveness	4.41	Very Good
Efficiency	Time Behavior	4.47	Very Good
	Resource Utilization	4.35	Very Good
Maintainability	Analyzability	4.34	Very Good
	Changeability	4.33	Very Good
	Stability	4.32	Very Good
	Testability	4.33	Very Good
Portability	Adaptability	4.30	Good
	Installability	4.31	Good
	Co-Existence	4.34	Very Good
	Replaceability	4.28	Good

Table 3. Acceptance Testing Results.

Acceptance testing results show that Medbuddy obtained the following rating on the acceptance attributes:

- 1) Functionality with suitability, accuracy, and interoperability criteria with mean scores ranging from 4.42 to 4.45,
- 2) Reliability with maturity, fault tolerance and recoverability criteria with mean scores of 4.38, 4.36, and 4.35, respectively,
- 3) Usability attribute with understandability, learnability, and operability criteria with mean scores 4.36, 4.40, and 4.45,
- 4) Efficiency with attractiveness, time behavior, and resource utilization of 4.41, 4.47, and 4.35, respectively,
- 5) Maintainability with criteria on analyzability, changeability, stability, and testability with scores 4.34, 4.33, 4.32, and 4.43, and
- 6) Portability considering adaptability, installability, co-existence, and replaceability criteria with mean scores of 4.30, 4.31, 4.34, and 4.28, respectively.

Across the evaluated metrics, Medbuddy achieved Very Good performance level consistently which is implied as the system is functionally reliable, efficient, usable, secure, and maintainable. These findings support Medbuddy as a suitable clinic-oriented digital consultation and health records management system tool especially for clinical healthcare facilities.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study addressed the challenges in the clinical healthcare services delivery in the country which is heavily relying on manual and paper-based appointment scheduling process and medical records keeping which makes the consultation process inconvenient for patients in various urban and rural areas alongside with limited post-consultation platform for doctor-patient updates and communication. As mentioned in the introduction, these limitations contribute to operational inefficiencies, lessen effective healthcare delivery, and increase patient inconvenience especially in a resource-limited clinical setting. Medbuddy was designed to support patient engagement, clinical diagnosis effectiveness, and coordination between the stakeholders of clinical procedure.

Medbuddy was able to integrate four core functional modules: consultation appointment scheduling, health records management, appointment status tracking and notification, and secure integrated messaging function. Software testing and evaluation was conducted in accordance primarily to ISO/IEC 9126 software quality standards and was observed to perform consistently across functionality, efficiency, usability, security, maintainability, and portability. As discussed in the results, acceptance testing yielded a Very Good rating, which is interpreted as the system being able to meet both performance and acceptance perception requirements.

In conclusion, the study successfully designed, implemented, and validated Medbuddy as a reliable and effective digital consultation-based health services platform and management system. The system was able to deliver the functionalities related to consultation process distributed to three main system roles according to design based on the testing and evaluation results garnering Very Good rating. More than its technical contributions, Medbuddy supported Sustainable Development Goal 3: Good Health and Well-being by the promotion of a system delivering timely access to healthcare consultation services in an efficient and centralized manner.

For further development, it was noted that the system should be extended through existing health information systems such as those provided by government healthcare-related agencies to enable seamless data collection and exchange as part of a centralized healthcare system. The inclusion of a language support for dialects in the country is also a good addition to the system to promote inclusivity among diverse Filipino people. Additionally, integrating advance data analytics for better

understanding of medical trends and ease of information acquisition is also recommended by medical practitioners and professionals.

CONCLUSION

The healthcare consultation process in the Philippines continues to face challenges due to manual appointment scheduling, fragmented medical records, and limited post-consultation communication, which negatively affect service efficiency and patient satisfaction. These limitations contribute to prolonged waiting times, administrative burden, and reduced continuity of care, particularly in clinics serving both urban and rural communities. Addressing these issues is essential in improving the overall quality and accessibility of healthcare services in the country.

To respond to these challenges, this study designed and developed MedBuddy, a web-based clinical consultation and health records management system that digitalizes core consultation workflows. The system integrates online appointment scheduling, centralized electronic health records, automated appointment status tracking with

notifications, and secure messaging functionalities within a role-based access control framework. This design enables effective coordination among patients, doctors, and clinic staff while ensuring data security and workflow separation.

RECOMMENDATION

To further enhance MedBuddy's functionality and long-term sustainability, future development should focus on improving system interoperability with existing national and local health information systems. Integration with government-supported healthcare platforms would allow seamless data exchange, improve continuity of care, and support a more unified healthcare ecosystem across multiple service providers.

It is also recommended to expand system accessibility by incorporating multilingual support, including Filipino and regional dialects, to accommodate diverse patient

populations. Enhancing mobile responsiveness and developing a dedicated mobile application could further improve accessibility, especially for users in remote areas with limited access to desktop devices. These improvements would help ensure broader adoption and usability across varying levels of digital literacy.

Lastly, future versions of MedBuddy may benefit from the integration of advanced analytics and decision-support tools to assist healthcare providers in identifying consultation patterns, managing clinic workloads, and improving clinical decision-making. Strengthening data security measures and conducting large-scale pilot implementations in both urban and rural clinics are also recommended to further validate system performance and maximize its contribution to efficient, inclusive, and sustainable healthcare service delivery.

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